

NEP 2020: A Critical Perspective Towards Multidisciplinary Approach in Education

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Abstract

The national education policy 2020 develops a new perspective towards our education system. It will play a significant role in integrating the various disciplines into a multidisciplinary form that will provide a great opportunity for learners to learn the new skills and become a competent individual. This will help to develop them holistically and make them a skilled learner according to the current need of developing nation. Therefore many courses have been introduced in undergraduate and master's level programs that also vocational disciplines. This paper mainly focuses towards multidisciplinary approach and its linkage with STEM education that brought many opportunities and challenges in our current education system.

Keywords: NEP-2020, Multidisciplinary education, STEM education.

Introduction

The multidisciplinary approach of education have been studied and practised in India since ancient time. Some of the famous universities like Takshashila and Nalanda university needs to impart holistic education to students by focusing towards overall development of their personality. The introduction of NEP 2020, brought a boom towards holistic and multidisciplinary education that aim to develop overall capacities of human beings i.e. intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional and moral in an integrated manner (NEP 2020). In this developing nation, there is requirement of competent and skilled individuals at workplace and in various institutions. Thus the STEM education play a significant role in incorporating the integrated approach of learning skills from various disciplines. The incorporation of arts and humanities in STEM education open the diverse learning platform for learners, therefore the STEM education is been modified into STEAM education.

This new education policy, also provide high quality and flexible curricular structure in multidisciplinary education by inclusion of multiple entry and exit credit points. The higher education system will further possess more innovative curricula covering multiple disciplines that will further include credit based courses. The academic bank of credit (ABC) will be formed that will digitally store academic credit point obtained by students while pursuing multidisciplinary courses. Thus for expanding the multidisciplinary education in India MERUs (Multidisciplinary Education and Research Universities) will be established that will help to meet the global standard of quality education. This can only be accomplished by paying major emphasis on research on various multidiscipline and their implementation in

higher education. Therefore this study mainly focus towards multidisciplinary approach in education that will lead the 21st century developing nation.

Objective

- 1 To study about the multidisciplinary approach in education and its linkage with STEM education as given in NEP 2020. Methodology.
- 2 In this study critical analysis of NEP 2020 policy document have been done that make this study conceptualized. In this study data had been collected by secondary sources like Online e-journals, articles, policy documents, encyclopedia, newspaper, blogs, etc.

Discussion

The approach of multidisciplinary education:

- In this 21st century there is demand of some major shift in our education system. One of the approach towards accomplishing that is given in NEP 2020 i.e. multidisciplinary education.
- The Policy states, “multidisciplinary and holistic education across the sciences, social sciences, arts, humanities, and sports for a multidisciplinary world in order to ensure the unity and integrity of all knowledge” (NEP, 2020). UNESCO has explained the “multidisciplinary approach as an approach to curriculum integration which focuses primarily on the different disciplines and the diverse perspectives they bring to illustrate a topic, theme or issue. A multidisciplinary curriculum is one in which the same topic is studied from the viewpoint of more than one discipline” (UNESCO, IBE).
- The International Bureau of Education defines multidisciplinary education as studying a topic from the viewpoint of more than one discipline. (Klaassen, 2018).
- The multidisciplinary approach of education plays a significant role in over all development of individual mentally, physically, emotionally, socially, etc. The holistic development of learner is not possible without incorporating multidisciplinary education in the curriculum.

- The integration of multidisciplinary education in higher education courses will bring new dimensions and opportunities for students professional development.
- Some of the multidisciplinary integrated courses in higher education are as follows- Integration of Scientific fields such as biology, chemistry, mathematics, statistics and

computer science in bioinformatics.

- The integrated B.Ed. course, integration of B.Ed. with B.A. gives the Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) i.e. the combination of B.A.-B.Ed. The Integration of arts, such as singing and painting, technology and digital arts, integration of vocational courses , such as Artificial Intelligence, Robotics in education, etc. as well as soft skills such as communication, discussion and debate.
- This could enhance creativity and innovation, critical thinking, problem solving abilities and also proves crucial to develop intellectual, social, psychological, emotional and aesthetic aspects of an individual.
- In this global era, interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approach in education help students to think creatively, critically and learn new competencies and skills as required in their professional development.
- In today's globalized and interconnected world, it is becoming important for professionals to be able to communicate and collaborate effectively with people from different cultural, linguistic, and disciplinary backgrounds.
- Interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary programs play a significant role in preparing students for such types of careers, as they provide students with the skills, ability and knowledge needed to work effectively with people from a variety of backgrounds.
- Thus multidisciplinary approach in education incorporates variety of disciplines and help students to think with a new frame of mind, generate new ideas and help in their holistic development.

Interpretation of term STEM and STEAM

Type Karna Ha Text Benefits of multidisciplinary approach in higher education

- It can incorporate different disciplines such as the humanities and arts with Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) to provide the accessibility of different

multidisciplinary courses that will open vast career opportunities for students.

- It may also increase the interest of students in research and innovation to explore the multidisciplinary approach in education with innovative mind set.
- The evaluation process in multidisciplinary education will also be based on formative assessment type rather than summative type of evaluation .
- The multidisciplinary education in colleges and universities provide vast opportunities to students , as they can choose the subject according to their interest which will further help student to enrich their professional career and add value to their life.
- The online education tools such as learning management system and open-distance learning help students living in remote area to study multidisciplinary education that will further help student to boost their career and personal growth.

Major challenges of multidisciplinary approach in higher education

- The biggest hurdle in accessing multidisciplinary education is with students living in remote areas where they don't possess proper infrastructure to access education.
- Its necessary to overcome the problem of accessibility, equality , affordability and reachability. Online and open-distance learning mode of education (NEP 2020) has set up to overcome the barrier of digital divide. According to NEP 2020 there is a target of achieving 50 per cent GER by 2035. To achieve this target, HE needs to be imparted by online teaching-learning platforms such as SWAYAM and MOOC platform.
- The proper training should be provided to teachers for accessibility of multidisciplinary education that can be understood clearly by students.
- The responsibility of teachers increases with multidisciplinary approach of education. It necessary to look out towards students performance as with the knowledge of multiple disciplines sometimes they lack the expertise in one domain. The teachers should be extra careful during the evaluation of student performance.
- Therefore for proper execution of the policy at all levels and across all institutions, the Central and State governments, UGC and RUSA, Universities, the Department of Education, and the governing bodies of various educational institutions must work together in a collaborative way.(NEP 2020)

Conclusion

The multidisciplinary approach of education opens a new dimensions of learning and vast career opportunities for students. In this competitive world of 21st century, multidisciplinary approach in education will play an important role in imparting skills and competencies to students that will help them in accessing various job opportunities. The STEAM incorporated with arts and humanities in education sector modify the curriculum and teaching strategies in every level of education. Now a certain problem in education can be deal with multiple perspective thus solving the problem from new mind set. As STEAM is a collaboration of different disciplines thus it provide huge opportunities for students to make career in different areas according to their interest. Its necessary to flourish the multidisciplinary education and make it accessible even in remote areas. This can be only achieve by open and distance learning , and modifying infrastructure in rural areas, so that students can access online education from various online learning platform such as SWAYAM,MOOC. Thus the multidisciplinary education play a significant role in imparting different hard and soft skills to individual i.e. the current requirement globally. This will also help in flourishing our education system and increasing the economy of our country

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